

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D3.2 GOhydro AI Models

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ACRONYMS LIST

CHSK	Crop Health Sensor Kit
CSU	Communication and Storage Unit
MMS	Multi-modal Sensor Kit
NCK	Nutrient-content Kit
PLS	Partial Least Squares
LMS	Least Mean Squares
SVR	Support Vector Regression
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CLNN	Cascade Learning Neural Networks

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report provides an overview of the operational framework and design of the GOhydro AI models, i.e., the components responsible for performing predictive analysis over the data collected via the Sensor Kit embedded in the GOhydro hydroponic platform.

The report describes in brief the baseline knowledge to which the models rely, the data over which it operates, and the algorithmic families that will be tested as real data are being collected during the GOhydro trials. Finally, the report clarifies the architectural placement of the AI components in the context of the data platform that serves the overall GOhydro solution.

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro aims to develop a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in any hydroponic installation. In the bigger picture, the project aspires to culminate in the production of a radical platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all and user-friendly tool applicable to all forms of urban farming.

Towards this objective, the provision of robust, accurate predictive models that will determine the state of the cultivation based on sensing data and provide actionable guidance to the users is one of the core aspirations of the project and the GOhydro product itself. In this context, WP3 aims to put in place the AI framework that will make the most of the available data and the deep insights built in the context of WP1 and constitute an effective and performant recommendation and decision support sub-system.

D3.2 deals with the design and development of such models that will fulfil the aforementioned analytical requirements. It aims, on one hand, to properly interpret and contextualise the available sensing data and their correlation to optimal cultivation settings as produced by WP2 and WP1 respectively. And on the other hand, implement them under the data platform architecture specified in D3.1 ensuring the efficient exposure of the analytical results to the GOhydro application and external/future applications.

The present report summarizes the data representation and technical choices for designing and implementing the models, as well as the establishment of their training and validation framework within the GOhydro data platform.

2 SCOPE OF AI PREDICTIVE COMPONENTS

2.1 OVERALL CONCEPT AND PURPOSE

In the context of GOhydro, AI components serve as the enabler of the monitoring and recommendation functions of the overall solution. The aim is for the data platform underlying the end-user application to continuously get informed of the state of a cultivation in a given installation, provide visual analytics to the user/manager of the platform, and forward tending tips to optimise the cultivation process.

Cultivation Optimisation is assessed against the optimal recipes as determined by WP1 studies, regarding the different microgreen species covered. Furthermore, they are modelled as correlative to the environmental conditions, as well as certain light and water parameters within the hydroponic unit. It is, moreover, measured by the physical and chemical parameters presented in deliverable D1.2.

The purpose of the models, is thus, to solve a *regression* problem associating the obtained measurements with the expected physical and chemical measurements of the resulting yield.

2.2 DATA REPRESENTATION

The data collected via the GOhydro Multi-modal Sensor Kit (MMS), and in particular its Crop Health Sensor Kit (CHSK) component, are cached into the platform's communication unit (CSU) and periodically sent via the relevant API calls to the underlying Qvantum instance. The data are annotated with identification information of the installation, and measurements are timestamped. JSON is used as the data exchange format between the communicating entities. An exemplary JSON structure with obfuscated data is presented in the following figure. For each data point, the exact timestamp of each measurement provided by the sensors incorporated in the CHSK is included along with the measured value, i.e. four different timeseries are taken into account for each cultivation setting.

```
{
  "_id": {
    "$oid": "62cd602880e2030f51b91d83"
  },
  "controller_id": "E4:5F:01:47:4C:71",
  "data_kits": [
    {
      "sensor_kit_id": "Mac Address of RaspberryPi-Zero2W",
      "data_points": [
        {
          "sensor": "PH_Meter",
          "value": "1",
          "timestamp": "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:sec"
        },
        {
          "sensor": "Air_Humidity",
          "value": "1",
          "timestamp": "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:sec"
        },
        {
          "sensor": "TDS_Meter",
          "value": "1",
          "timestamp": "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:sec"
        },
        {
          "sensor": "UV_light",
          "value": "1",
          "timestamp": "YYYY-MM-DDThh:mm:sec"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 1: Sample of JSON data structure communicated from the CSU to the Data Platform

Furthermore, each training session accepts as input the parameters of the recipe applied in the current cultivation cycle, as well as the measures for determining yield quantity and quality reported in deliverable D4.1. These are measured post-facto after the yield has been collected and uploaded to the data platform with the same identifiers, in order to be incorporated in the training set.

3 DESIGN & EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 CANDIDATE AI METHODOLOGIES

As indicated in the preliminary stages of the project, the broader approach to be adopted for the GOhydro AI models is to combine different methods and strategies in combination, in order to overcome the general problem of low training data volumes in the agricultural experiments domain.

Given the data and experimental characteristics of the GOhydro case, we will put in place different modules implementing relevant Analytical and ML algorithms and examine different combinations of theirs during the experimental stage (when data are available from the first pilot growth cycles) to establish the finalised AI module.

Indicatively, components implementing the following approaches have been setup towards the production of the first AI component prototype. On the one hand, we incorporate different regression methodologies, including:

- a. **Partial Least Squares regression (PLS)**: the method reduces the variables used to predict, to a smaller set of predictors. These predictors are then used to perform a (linear) regression. It is widely used in domains relevant to GOhydro, such as bioinformatics and sensometrics.
- b. **Least Mean Squares regression (LMS)**: the Least Squares family of algorithms aim to approximate given values by incrementally finding an optimal fitting function between them and the input variables. Optimality is determined by minimising an error function over the residuals (i.e. differences between given and observed values). LMS is one of the most potent approaches for this minimisation problem, and can use different variations of gradient descent approaches for the tested functions.
- c. **Support Vector Regression (SVR)**: In accordance with the general principles of Support Vector Machines, the basic idea behind SVR is to find the best fit line for a dataset. In SVR, the best fit line is the hyperplane that has the maximum number of points. Unlike other regression models that try to minimize the error between the real and predicted value, the SVR tries to fit the best line within a threshold value. It is thus best suitable for relatively low-volume datasets, as it is not computationally scalable.
- d. **Random Forests**: Random forests is a Supervised Machine Learning Algorithm, and specifically an ensemble learning method, that is used widely in both classification and regression problems. It builds decision trees on different samples and takes their majority vote for classification and average in case of regression. While it generally performs better in classification problems, the approach can produce good result to regression problems where there are not explicitly stated correlation between the input variables.

All the above techniques can be incorporated in different architectures of Neural Networks and different training paradigms, such as **Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)** and **Cascade Learning Networks (CLNN)**. We will test different connectivity and training techniques in the context of experimenting with the different approaches.

In the cases of techniques that require a relatively larger amount of data for their proper training, we will use synthetic datasets produced via stochastic generators and based on the realistic data samples reported by the pilots.

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP WITHIN THE GOHYDRO DATA PLATFORM

As detailed in deliverable D3.1, the produced AI models are integrated into the overall GOhydro data infrastructure and constitute the *AI Pipeline* layer of the platform (lower left of Figure 1). In essence,

the AI Pipeline entails the training and operationalisation of the models, using data as they are collected in the persistence layer.

The training part is profile-independent, i.e., all collected data are used for re-training and re-calibrating the components, taking into account the particularities of a setup as additional features (e.g., geographical location of the installation). In contrast, the execution workflow uses the latest version of the models as derived from their latest training session, to analyse and produce recommendations for a given installation/user.

All AI components are implemented in Python and containerised in Docker instances for their deployment under the Quantum platform. Their communication with the persistence layer is realised via the API calls exposed by the latter’s databases, to collect both measurement and installation-specific data and build the overall training datasets and inputs for the models.

Figure 2: GOhydro data platform - high-level architecture

4 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

The report serves as a companion to the GOhydro AI models implementation, providing a high-level overview of the design and development considerations of the relevant components.

It is meant as a low-tech summary of the involved technologies and architectural choices, with the programmatic documentation of the components being a distinct outcome of the relevant GOhydro activities, to be available online and attached to the actual source code of the components.

As the described solution evolve and mature, the report will reflect these developments, updating the relevant descriptions and providing links to the relevant repositories where source code and documentation reside.

The next step in the activities pertaining to AI model development is the initiation of testing and training steps, as data collected via the experimental pilots are made available. The first deployment of operational models within the GOhydro data platform and their respective evaluation will follow, with the continuous re-training/re-deployment operations to be enacted right afterwards.